

Horizontal Gene Transfer of Antibiotic Resistance Genes in Algae-Bacteria Wastewater Biofilms: Mechanisms, Drivers, and Implications

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Abstract

The increasing prevalence of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) in wastewater environments has raised significant environmental and public health concerns. Algae-bacteria biofilms have emerged as promising systems for wastewater treatment due to their synergistic interactions and high pollutant removal efficiency. However, their complex structure and microbial composition may also create favorable conditions for the persistence and dissemination of ARGs. This review provides a focused overview of ARG occurrence, horizontal gene transfer (HGT) mechanisms, and key influencing factors in algae-bacteria biofilms. Current evidence indicates that ARGs are present in both intracellular and extracellular forms, with the extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) matrix playing a critical role in their retention and stability. Conjugation is likely the dominant HGT pathway, while transformation and transduction may also contribute under biofilm conditions. Factors such as antibiotic pressure, extracellular DNA availability, algal-driven redox gradients, nutrient conditions, and microbial community interactions collectively regulate ARG transfer. HGT can enhance biofilm resilience under stress but may also alter microbial community structure and affect treatment performance, particularly nitrogen removal. Overall, algae-bacteria biofilms represent both effective treatment systems and potential reservoirs for ARG dissemination. Further research is needed to clarify HGT pathways, identify ARG hosts, and better understand algal-bacterial interactions to support safer wastewater treatment applications.

Keywords: *antibiotic resistance genes, horizontal gene transfer, algae-bacteria biofilm, wastewater treatment, extracellular polymeric substances, microbial interactions.*

Introduction

The rapid emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) have become a major environmental and public health concern (Aminudin et al., 2026). Wastewater treatment plants are recognized as important reservoirs of ARGs, as they receive antibiotics, resistant bacteria, and other contaminants from domestic, industrial, and hospital sources. Although these systems are designed to remove pollutants, they may also provide favorable conditions for the persistence and dissemination of ARGs.

Biofilms play a key role in wastewater treatment processes due to their high microbial density, structural stability, and metabolic versatility (Ugwu et al., 2025). In particular, algae-bacteria biofilms have gained increasing attention for their ability to enhance pollutant removal through synergistic interactions.

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Microalgae can supply oxygen via photosynthesis, supporting bacterial nitrification, while bacteria provide carbon dioxide and nutrients that sustain algal growth (Lee, Im, & Gil, 2022). These interactions improve overall treatment performance, especially for nitrogen removal.

However, the complex structure of algae-bacteria biofilms may also create conditions that promote horizontal gene transfer (HGT) (Li et al., 2023). The proximity of microorganisms, together with the presence of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) and extracellular DNA, can facilitate the exchange of genetic material, including ARGs (Sharif & Yadav, 2025). In addition, environmental factors such as antibiotic pressure, nutrient availability, and redox gradients generated by algal activity may further influence gene transfer processes.

Despite the increasing application of algae-bacteria biofilms in wastewater treatment, their role in ARG dissemination remains insufficiently understood. Most current knowledge of HGT comes from bacterial biofilm systems, while evidence from algae-bacteria biofilms remains limited.

Therefore, this review aims to provide a focused overview of ARG occurrence, horizontal gene transfer mechanisms, and key influencing factors in algae-bacteria biofilms. The potential impacts of ARG transfer on biofilm function and wastewater treatment performance are also discussed to support the development of safer and more sustainable biofilm-based treatment systems.

Materials and Methods

A literature review was conducted using databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, and ScienceDirect. Relevant studies were identified using keywords related to antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), horizontal gene transfer (HGT), and algae-bacteria biofilms. Peer-reviewed articles focusing on wastewater treatment systems were selected and grouped into themes, including ARG occurrence, transfer mechanisms, influencing factors, and biofilm performance.

Results

Occurrence of ARGs in Algae-Bacteria Wastewater Biofilms

Antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) are widely occurring in wastewater environments where residual antibiotics, bacteria, and mobile genetic elements coexist (Berglund, Ebmeyer, Kristiansson, & Larsson, 2023). Wastewater biofilms play a crucial role in the spread of ARG due to their dense microbial structure, extracellular polymeric substances (EPS), and close cell-to-cell contact, which can retain genetic material and promote gene exchange. Recent reviews and wastewater biofilm studies described biofilm systems as plausible hotspots for the ARG spread and accumulation, especially in the presence of mobile genetic elements (Buelow et al., 2023; Saini, Tewari, Dwivedi, & Sharma, 2023). Compared to conventional bacterial biofilms, the evidence of ARG spread in algae-bacteria biofilm systems remains limited. Still, existing studies already show that ARGs are detectable in microalgal-bacterial wastewater treatment systems and should not be ignored. A recent review on microalgal-bacteria consortia noted that these systems interact closely with the migration of ARG processes. Another review on antibiotics removal in microalgal-bacterial symbiotic systems emphasized that even though the treatment performance is improved with microalgal-bacterial symbiosis, ARGs generated under antibiotic stress remain a serious threat (Gong et al., 2024). Current evidence from algal-bacterial granular sludge and symbiotic biofilms suggests that antibiotic exposure and shifts in microbial community structure influence the occurrence of ARG (Malla et al., 2025). A 2022 study found that microalgal growth on bacterial granules reduced the abundance of ARGs and ARG-host bacteria, but ARGs were not eliminated (Liu et al., 2022).

Although there are limited datasets related to microalgal-bacteria biofilms with ARGs, the ARG profiles reported in wastewater biofilms systems more broadly provide a useful reference point for the types of genes likely to occur in these systems studies and reviews of wastewater and aquatic biofilms frequently report ARGs related to tetracycline, sulfonamides, β -lactams, quinolones, and macrolides, often together with class 1 integrons and other mobile genetic elements that support transfer potential. The same resistance categories are highly relevant to algae-bacteria biofilms because such systems are commonly proposed for treating antibiotic-containing wastewater, including wastewater contaminated with sulfonamides and tetracyclines (Bradshaw, 2025). ARGs in biofilms occur not only intracellularly but also as extracellular DNA retained within the EPS matrix (Wang et al., 2024). In algae-bacteria biofilms, this matrix may protect DNA and enhance its persistence, making extracellular ARGs an important component of resistance dissemination (Li et al., 2024).

Overall, current evidence suggests that algae-bacteria biofilms can harbor ARGs and mobile genetic elements, although some studies report lower ARG abundance than in bacterial-only systems. The main gap is the limited understanding of dominant ARGs, their hosts, and their links to extracellular DNA and transfer pathways in these biofilms.

Mechanisms of HGT in Algae-Bacteria Biofilms

Horizontal gene transfer (HGT) in algae-bacteria biofilms mainly occurs through conjugation, transformation, and transduction, which are also the major pathways responsible for antibiotic resistance gene (ARG) dissemination in wastewater biofilms more broadly. Biofilm conditions are especially favorable for HGT because high cell density, close microbial contact, and matrix-associated DNA can increase the probability of gene exchange.

Conjugation is generally considered the most important mechanism in biofilm-associated ARG transfer. In this process, plasmids or other conjugative mobile genetic elements are transferred through direct cell-to-cell contact. Because algae-bacteria biofilms provide stable microbial aggregation and prolonged physical proximity, they may promote conjugative exchange between bacterial members of the consortium (Virolle, Goldlust, Djerroun, Bigot, & Lesterlin, 2020).

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of Bacterial Conjugation

Transformation involves the uptake of extracellular DNA released from lysed cells into the surrounding matrix. This pathway is particularly relevant in biofilms because extracellular DNA can accumulate within EPS and remain available for uptake by competent bacteria. In algae-bacteria biofilms, the EPS-rich

matrix may therefore act as a reservoir for extracellular ARGs and support their persistence and potential transfer (Yu, Wang, Henderson, & Guo, 2022).

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram of Gene Transformation

Transduction is mediated by bacteriophages, which transfer genetic material between bacteria during infection. Although this mechanism is less frequently discussed than conjugation in wastewater biofilms, it is still recognized as a possible route for ARG dissemination and should not be excluded from algae-bacteria systems (Wachino, 2025).

Figure 3. Schematic Diagram of Gene Transduction

Overall, conjugation is likely the dominant pathway, while transformation and transduction may also contribute depending on extracellular DNA availability, phage activity, and biofilm structure. However, the relative importance of each mechanism in algae-bacteria biofilms is still poorly resolved.

Factors Influencing HGT in Algae-Bacteria Biofilms

The horizontal transfer of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) in algae-bacteria biofilms is influenced by multiple environmental and biological factors. Among these, antibiotic selective pressure is a primary

driver, as it promotes the proliferation of resistant bacteria and enhances the maintenance and transfer of ARGs within the biofilm. The extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) matrix also plays a key role by retaining extracellular DNA and facilitating close microbial contact, both of which increase the likelihood of gene exchange. In addition, the presence of extracellular DNA (eDNA) within the matrix provides a reservoir for transformation-based ARG transfer (Flemming, Neu, & Wozniak, 2007). Unique to algae-bacteria systems, algal oxygen release creates redox gradients within the biofilm, leading to spatially distinct aerobic and anoxic zones. These microenvironments can influence microbial activity and potentially affect HGT processes. Furthermore, organic substrates and nutrient availability regulate microbial growth and metabolic activity, indirectly shaping ARG transfer dynamics (Hu, Liu, Wen, Zhou, & Wang, 2025). Finally, microbial community composition and interactions are critical, as shifts in dominant taxa and functional groups can alter both the abundance of ARG hosts and the potential for gene exchange. Overall, HGT in algae-bacteria biofilms is controlled by a combination of antibiotic pressure, EPS and eDNA availability, redox conditions, nutrient status, and microbial community dynamics.

Effects of HGT on Biofilm Function and Performance

Horizontal gene transfer (HGT) of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) can significantly influence the structure and function of algae-bacteria biofilms. The acquisition of ARGs may enhance microbial tolerance to antibiotics, allowing resistant populations to persist and dominate under stress conditions, which can alter overall microbial community composition. These shifts may affect key biofilm functions, particularly nitrogen removal processes, as changes in functional bacteria can influence nitrification and denitrification performance. In some cases, the enrichment of resistant but functionally less efficient microorganisms may reduce treatment efficiency, while in others, adaptation may help maintain system stability under antibiotic stress. HGT can also contribute to biofilm adaptation and resilience, enabling microbial communities to survive fluctuating environmental conditions. However, this adaptive advantage is coupled with the risk of increased ARG dissemination within the system. Overall, HGT plays a dual role by supporting biofilm stability under stress while potentially compromising treatment performance and promoting the spread of antibiotic resistance.

Figure 4. Conceptual Diagram of the Effects of HGT on Biofilm

Discussion

The findings of this review suggest that algae-bacteria biofilms function as both treatment systems and potential reservoirs for ARG dissemination. While these systems are effective in removing pollutants, the coexistence of antibiotics, resistant bacteria, and mobile genetic elements creates conditions that may facilitate horizontal gene transfer (HGT).

Compared with conventional bacterial biofilms, algae-bacteria biofilms introduce additional complexity through algal-bacterial interactions. The release of oxygen by microalgae generates redox gradients within the biofilm, which can influence microbial metabolism and potentially affect HGT processes. At the same time, the well-developed EPS matrix enhances microbial aggregation and retains extracellular DNA, further increasing the likelihood of gene exchange. Although some studies report reduced ARG abundance in algae-bacteria systems, this does not necessarily indicate the elimination of resistance risks. Instead, it suggests that these systems may mitigate but not fully prevent ARG persistence and transfer. The presence of extracellular ARGs and mobile genetic elements highlights the potential for continued dissemination even under improved treatment performance.

Another important insight is that HGT is closely linked to biofilm structure and community dynamics. Changes in microbial composition, driven by antibiotic pressure or environmental conditions, can alter both the abundance of ARG hosts and the efficiency of gene transfer pathways. This indicates that ARG dissemination is not controlled by a single factor, but by the combined effects of biological, chemical, and physical conditions within the biofilm. Despite increasing interest, direct evidence of HGT specifically in algae-bacteria biofilms remains limited. Most current understanding is extrapolated from bacterial biofilm studies, highlighting a key research gap. In particular, the relative contribution of conjugation, transformation, and transduction, as well as the identification of dominant ARG hosts and transfer routes, require further investigation.

Overall, algae-bacteria biofilms represent a promising yet complex system, where pollutant removal and ARG dissemination occur simultaneously. A better understanding of these interactions is essential for optimizing wastewater treatment processes while minimizing the risk of antibiotic resistance spread.

Conclusion

This review demonstrates that algae-bacteria biofilms are important systems for both wastewater treatment and the persistence of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs). ARGs are present in these biofilms in both intracellular and extracellular forms, supported by the EPS matrix, which enhances their retention and stability. Horizontal gene transfer (HGT) plays a central role in ARG dissemination, with conjugation likely dominating, while transformation and transduction may also contribute under biofilm conditions. These processes are regulated by multiple factors, including antibiotic pressure, extracellular DNA availability, algal-driven redox gradients, nutrient conditions, and microbial community interactions. Importantly, HGT can enhance biofilm adaptation and resilience under antibiotic stress, but may also alter microbial community structure and affect treatment performance, particularly nitrogen removal. This highlights the dual role of algae-bacteria biofilms as both effective treatment systems and potential reservoirs for ARG spread.

Overall, this study provides a focused understanding of ARG occurrence, transfer mechanisms, and influencing factors in algae-bacteria biofilms. However, key uncertainties remain regarding the dominant HGT pathways, ARG hosts, and the specific role of algal-bacterial interactions in regulating gene transfer. Addressing these gaps is essential for developing safer and more sustainable biofilm-based wastewater treatment technologies.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest

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